

Community Collaboration Boardgame

Intro

How to improve the community collaboration?

Aim

Aim is to get to the end. Asking help is the key to the success.

Players: 2-9

Age: over 7

Materials: game board, dice, agent figures

How to play the game(rules)

Youngest player will begin.

Throw the dice and go forward.

If you go to the box with ladders answer the question and use the ladders.

If you go to the box with snake, you have to go to the box where snake ends.

First one in the end wins.

Co-designed and Co-created by

Annukka Juutinen (UEF Teacher Training School, Finland)

Jaana Räisänen (UEF Teacher Training School, Finland)

Lavinia Halász (Don Orione, Romania)

COMMUNITY

<p>If you know how to get to know the community go to 18. If not to 14.</p>		<p>You call to a company and they are very negative or against the idea. You get disappointed. Go to the beginning.</p>	<p>FINISH You have to have the equal number.</p>
<p>Your friend knows a good company to contact with.</p>		<p>You are a professional in OSS and can help your community to become the drivers of change.</p>	<p>The company never answers your calls. WAIT FOR ONE ROUND.</p>
<p>The school manager helps you.</p>			
<p>START</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>Listen to your colleague. She/He has good tips.</p>	<p>2</p>

EduDrivers Boardgame

Intro

Are you a teacher? Do you like traveling? Would you like to explore different learning systems, methodologies and activities outside your school curriculum? Then this is a game for you! Open Science Schooling is here to open a new world in front of you! Would you be lucky enough to reach your goals?

Aim

The aim of the game is to include OSS methodology and activities into the school curriculum and overcome any obstacles that will come into your way. The winner is the player that reaches the quarter 34 first.

Players: 4

Ages: 6+

Materials: game board, dice, agent figures

How to play the game (rules)

At the beginning each player rolls the dice. The player has the highest number in the dice starts first. Each player has one turn. On the game board there are six (6) ladders, six (6) arrows and three (3) blue quarters; the quarters with the ladders travel you up as they symbolize the skills that will let you include OSS methodology into the school curriculum, the quarters with the arrows travel you down as they symbolize the difficulties that you are coping with and the blue quarters stuck you in the Mediterranean sea, the Black sea and the Ireland sea so you lose one turn.

Ladders

2 = When taking up a mission, pick up the mission closer to the topics of the school curriculum.

4 = When creating tasks for your lessons, try to keep them up-to-date, real-life based or providing real-life skills.

9 = Ask the subject teachers to specify the tasks and the activities of their lessons for them to have keywords points and tasks connected to the project mission.

13 = Encourage your students to involve parents or other family members into the project activities. In this way you will gain closer connection between student-family-school.

15 = Encourage your student to self-educational activities to get background information to use during the lessons and the project activities.

18 = Praise and evaluate the students and teachers that are mostly involved in the missions.

Arrows

8 = Time is not in favour of the teachers. The didactic hour is not enough for the teachers to incorporate different activities that need extra time to be implemented.

10 = Teachers may not know any innovative methods to use in their lessons other than the traditional ways following the schoolbooks.

25 = Many teachers even nowadays are not familiar with the use of technology inside the classes and the curriculum doesn't involve any new technology.

28 = Not all of the lessons from the school curriculum can be connected to special subjects and scientific fields.

30 = The didactic material and planning is focused on the final exams. That leads to the fact that whatever is not going to be examined at the end of the school year doesn't matter to the teachers/students/parents.

Co-designed and Co-created by:

Liudmila Gertune (Pasvalio School, Lithuania)

Janne Heiskanen (Teacher Training School Joensuu, Finland)

Eugenia Moysidou (Platon School, Greece)

Levent Hıdır (Teknik Anadolu Lisesi, Turkey)

Rebels Boardgame

Intro

The *Rebel boardgame* wants to reveal the real school life of students. The players (students or teachers as well) cross 43 situations which can motivate or demotivate the students. The students' motivation in school activities is a topic often analyzed and debated by teachers. It is more and more hard to motivate students to learn and also to do extracurricular activities in school. This game wants to help students and teachers to connect each other and find solutions for the lack of motivation.

Aim

Giving concrete examples of what students can do to be more than a simple learner, to be an active member in their school environment and also in their community.

Players: 2 - 4

Age: 10+

Materials: game board, dice, agent figures, colored cards

How to play the game (rules)

1. The player who rolls the biggest dice starts the game
2. Player rolls the dice. It moves forward in the boxes as much as the incoming number.
3. If the player's pawn has landed on the number, the written action is applied by looking at its equivalent in the good/bad practice table.
4. If the pawn is in the orange zone, a question is drawn from the question card and answered.
5. If the pawn lands on the other figure and the empty box, the player rests for that round.
6. The first to get to the 44th box wins the game.

Co-designed and Co-created by:

Ioana Drugas (Liceul Don Orione, Romania)

Ilias Batzogiannis (Platon School, Greece)

Hanne Vähäkoski (UEF Teacher Training School, Finland)

Neslihan Turan Solmaz (Teknik Anadolu Lisesi, Turkey)

Rebel Board Game – Schools as Drivers of Change

1. YOU HELP YOUR FRIEND TO SOLVE AN ARGUMENT WITH TEACHER	+2	21. REWARD WHEN SOMETHING IS DONE WELL	+3
2. YOU ARE BULLYING IN YOUR SCHOOL	-2	22. APPROVE NEW IDEAS	+2
3. YOU MISS YOUR MORNING SESSION	-1	23. CRITICIZE WHEN THINGS DON'T GO WELL	-2
4. YOU DO EXTRA WORK IN YOUR LESSON	+1	24. ENCOURAGE PEOPLE TO DO WHAT THEY ARE DOING	+1
5. YOU ARE ON TIME EVERY LESSON FOR 1 MONTH	+3	25. HELP PEOPLE WHEN THEY ARE IN NEED	+5
6. YOU LEARN A NEW TRICK IN BASKETBALL LESSON	+3	26. DISCOURAGE PEOPLE WHEN THEY WANT TO MAKE A CHANGE	-3
7. SOMEONE FALLS DOWN AND YOU HELP HIM/HER TO NURSE	+2	27. YOU ARE MAKING FUN OF OTHERS' IDEAS	-2
8. YOU CHEAT ON A TEST	-2	28. IGNORE OTHERS WHAT THEY ARE SAYING	-3
9. YOU LIE TO THE TEACHER	-3	29. YOU ARE AFRAID OF DOING SOMETHING IN A NEW WAY	-2
10. YOU FAIL THE TEST BECAUSE YOU DIDN'T READ	-3	30. YOU TAKE CARE OF THE OTHERS	+3
11. MAKE EYE CONTACT WITH UNMOTIVATED STUDENTS	+6	31. GIVE BADGES FOR COMPLETING TASKS	+1
12. BE SARCASTIC! HOW DOES IT FEEL?	-5	32. HAVE A TRIP OUTSIDE OF SCHOOL TO OBSERVE SOMETHING	+2
13. BE MORE FOCUSED ON UNMOTIVATED STUDENTS	+5	33. DO NOT CONNECT THINGS TAUGHT WITH EVERYDAY LIFE	-6
14. YOU DEVELOP ONE-TO-ONE DISCUSSION WITH UNMOTIVATED STUDENTS	+3	34. TELL THE STUDENTS EXACTLY WHAT TO DO AND GIVE THEM NO SPACE	-2
15. YOU ARE NOT PAYING ATTENTION TO UNMOTIVATED STUDENTS	-8	35. CALL A SPECIALIST TO DISCUSS WITH YOUR STUDENTS	+2
16. PROVIDE GOOD THOUGHTS AND WORDS TO THE PEOPLE	+2	36. USE A GAME (DIGITAL OR BOARD) INSIDE YOUR CLASS FOR TEACHING	+4
17. YOU ARE ALWAYS SERIOUS (NOT SMILING)	-2	37. ASK THEM WHAT THEY WANT TO LEARN ABOUT	+2
18. YOU ARE FOCUSED ONLY ON BASIC CURRICULA	-2	38. CRITICIZE AN IDEA OF ONE OF YOUR STUDENTS	-2
19. VALIDATE WHAT THE UNMOTIVATED STUDENTS ARE DOING WELL	+1	39. "TRADITIONAL TEACHING"	-4
20. YOU ARE CRITICIZING A LOT	-1	40. ASSIGN TOO HARD EXERCISES THAT THE STUDENTS ARE NOT ABLE TO COMPLETE	-3
BAD PRACTICE		GOOD PRACTICE	

WISH

REDEK

ARE CLOSE

41		!		42	!	!	43	44
	38			39		40		
36							37	
	33			34	35			
	29		30		31		32	
			25		26	27	28	
19		20	21	22			23	24
14	15	16			17	18		
7			8	9	10	11	12	13
START	1	2		3	4		5	6